

The Five ‘D’s of Friction

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1 Summary

Friction allows us to walk and drive, it enables many technologies but at the same time it also accounts for significant energy losses, it holds glaciers in place while it also drives earthquakes, In spite of significant research effort, some basic phenomena that govern friction remain elusive. Consequently, seemingly insignificant changes to a system, as simple as a slight change in boundary conditions, can unexpectedly trigger different physical mechanisms [1]. Zooming in, at the micrometre scale a frictional configuration comprises two rough surfaces, consisting of ‘hills’ and ‘valleys’, pressed together. Those local ‘hills’ (asperities) that touch can be thought of as being ‘glued’ together. A surface can only move forward compared to the other, i.e. slip, when all contacts detach. These detachments do not occur independently, but instead interact and organise into collective events. Interestingly, it is not quite understood how such an event nucleates. Over the past two years, the Principal Investigator (PI) has successfully developed a novel model that, for the first time, allows a systematic identification of the dominant nucleation mechanism. The analysis calls for ideas from statistical physics, while the model owes its effectiveness to continuum mechanics and numerical discretisation using finite elements. The PI’s dual expertise in continuum mechanics and its numerical treatment *and* experience in a theoretical physics lab, puts the PI in the perfect position to, for the first time, unravel the nucleation of slip, and rationalise its macroscopic consequences.

The following three scenarios of nucleation are possible. (1) *Percolation*: Asperities detach at different, uncorrelated, locations. (2) *Avalanches*: A sequence of asperity detachments that trigger each other in a region that grows in a fractal manner, and that can eventually be stopped by the disorder. (3) *Fracture*: A rupture front travels ballistically through the system. The goal of this project is to obtain a mechanism map, indicating which scenario dominates under which conditions, along the following five axes (*the five ‘D’s’*) that govern friction. (a) *Disorder*: Different (spatial) distributions of contact strengths and possible spatial correlations. (b) *Dissipation*: Energy dissipation at the frictional interface. (c) *Drive*: The way in which the system is driven (imposed strain or stress, homogeneous or inhomogeneous). (d) *Dimensionality*: The difference between slender or two-dimensional and full three-dimensional configurations. (e) *Delay*: The effect of aging of the frictional interface. Through constructing this map a thorough understanding of the physics is sought, by analysis of simulations but also by constructing and analysing mean field models. This mechanism map will then be coupled to the different observables that are available: released energy, or stress drop; rupture front dynamics; avalanche size distributions; earthquake precursors; and phenomenological friction laws. This study will unravel what crucial differences between seemingly similar systems lead to different observations, and, vice versa, what a combination of observations teaches us about the state of the system. The current work by the PI and co-workers, has resulted in the partial exploration of one axis of the proposed mechanism map: that of dissipation. It was found that in an overdamped limit, nucleation proceeds through avalanches, that are in the same universality class as predicted by mean field depinning theories, while in the inertial regime it proceeds by fracture that appears to be nucleated by avalanches.

The simple but efficient continuum model that the PI has developed and used, comprises a frictional interface embedded as a weak layer between two elastic bodies. This weak layer consists of a disordered set of blocks which mimic the behaviour of the asperity contacts. Each block behaves elastically up to a local yield stress, and, upon reaching this yield stress, the block releases its elastic energy and adopts a new yield stress. Owing to the continuum formulation, the dynamics along the interface and throughout the bulk are treated without additional assumptions through numerical solutions using the Finite Element Method. This provides access to observables with a clear meaning, and is fully in line with the PI’s expertise.

This model is well suited for the proposed project as it is formulated at a level where one may expect to capture the nucleation of slip, and measure slip dynamics and macroscopic observables such as stress drops. In contrast to existing approaches, it enables, for the first time, all systematic variations that are needed to unravel the nucleation of slip.

2 Current state of research in the field

A historical perspective

Solid-solid friction is one of the oldest subjects of scientific research. In fact the first systematic study dates back to Leonardo da Vinci [2, 3]. Da Vinci did a series of experiments (see Infobox 1) in which he measured the force that is needed to commence the sliding of a rectangular block over a flat surface, for different combinations of the block's weight and area of contact with the sliding surface. As a result he reported that the amount of frictional resistance is proportional to the weight of the block, but, most remarkably, and counter-intuitive to many, that this resistance does not depend on the contact area. Especially the latter observation took several centuries to be rationalised (see Infobox 2). The crucial insight was that in fact any surface is rough at the scale of micrometres [4–11], so that the contact of two solids can be thought of as two 'alpine' landscapes pressed together by the weight of the upper body. The 'hills' are thereby commonly referred to as asperities. Consequently only a small fraction of the projected, or apparent, contact area actually is in contact. To reconcile the experimental observations one can argue that the few asperities that are actually in contact carry an enormous normal load (due to the small real area of contact) and must behave plastically, i.e. respond by a constant stress. In terms of sliding, the consequence of this realisation is that the asperities detach under shear when a certain critical (yield) shear stress is attained [5]. If one also makes the argument that contacts age, in this picture leading to a higher local yield stress [12, 13], one can reconcile that [14, 15]: (i) The frictional resistance increases with the wait time since the last sliding [16–19]. (ii) When sliding at a constant velocity, the frictional resistance decreases with increasing sliding velocity (contacts are younger at a higher velocity). More formally one can formulate a friction 'law' known as the "rate-and-state" law [18, 20] (see Infobox 3). Although microscopic arguments underlay this law, a direct connection has not been established, so that it remains essentially phenomenological. Nonetheless, it has proven to be descriptive for many frictional systems, and it is therefore also commonly used as input to explain macroscopic phenomena in friction, ranging from industrial applications to the sliding of tectonic plates that drives earthquakes.

Besides the branch of engineering models, another important scientific branch in friction research is dedicated to trying to understand and characterise what happens at small scales, see Fig. 1. At the micro- and nanometre scales many fascinating topics are considered that include (list and references far from conclusive): What effects atomistic arrangements (or a lack thereof) have on the intrinsic adhesion [22, 23]; How asperities are formed by plasticity of the material [24–27], or its by its fracture or wear [28]; etc.

These branches, that together form the community of tribology [3], each focus on a particular scale whereby scale bridging proceeds through model predictions. In

Infobox 1. Da Vinci's experiments.

Leonardo da Vinci very systematically studied friction, as can be observed from his drawings such as the ones below (collected by [2]). Notice Da Vinci's style of writing in mirror image, which he allegedly did to avoid eavesdropping.

He observed that the friction force is:

- proportional to the weight
 $F \propto W$
- independent of the contact area
 $\partial F / \partial A_0 = 0$
(F needed to start sliding is the same for all depicted systems).

Figure 1. Different scales of friction [21].

such picture one completely ignores that asperity detachments do not occur independently, but instead interact and organise into collective effects. There exists now strong evidence that friction is not an intrinsic property of the surface, but rather a system property [1], these collective effects thereby form a missing piece of the puzzle, as indicated in Fig. 1. It is at this mesoscale that this Ambizione project is proposed: there where the disorder, introduced at the microscale, matters, as it organises collective events with significant macroscopic consequences. The remainder of this proposal focusses only on that scale and on the macroscopic consequences of such collective effects.

Friction is avalanches

One important branch of research that studies collective effects in friction originated from the very simple discrete model due to Burridge and Knopoff [29], in which a set of point masses connected through springs are subjected to some phenomenological friction force and a mechanical drive (see Infobox 4). An important picture that emerged from this branch of research is that of self-organised criticality as proposed by Bak and Tang [38]. In the context of friction, it refers to the fact that triggering of slip in one point can trigger an avalanche, when, through elastic interaction, the detachment of one point triggers slip in surrounding points. In a disordered system, a competition exists between the driving force and the pinning force introduced by the disorder. In the picture of self-organised criticality the system operates around a critical driving force that balances the force introduced by the disorder. Consequently, avalanches can be pinned (stopped) by the disorder. For this model it was found that, because of this competition, the distribution of avalanches is scale-free – avalanches can be of any possible size, i.e. their distribution follows a power law (see [39] and references therein). It remains to be verified if such a picture also holds for more realistic model, and how, in such an environment, the avalanches can be characterised.

Friction is fracture

It has also been argued a front of asperity detachments propagates ballistically along the entire interface as a ‘zipper-like opening’ or a sort of propagating fracture. Note that, in contrast to a real fracture, (i) the path of the fracture is predetermined to be the frictional interface, and that (ii) as the interface continues to bare a normal load it continuously carries a shear load as new contacts are formed all the time. The picture of fracture was very elegantly demonstrated experimentally by Fineberg and co-workers [1, 40, 42–45] (see Infobox 5). They performed precise measurements of the change of the local area of contact, and of the strain field in the solid, close to the frictional interface. This gave them an insight in the rupture front’s velocity and the elastic strain in the bulk. They were able to obtain a close match of the entire tensorial strain field to a classic prediction made for fracture. This prediction is known as the theory of Linear Elastic Fracture Mechanics [46–55], LEFM in short, that is greatly influenced by the work of Griffith [56].

In the language of fracture one asks at which size a seed grows unstably over the entire length of the interface. Griffith made a simple energetic argument stating that when the energy released by the growth of the fracture exceeds the energy cost of advancing the fracture (the fracture toughness), the fracture will grow unstably. LEFM adds to this a full description of the stress field around the fracture. In the experiments, Fineberg and co-workers essentially calibrate the fracture toughness, and compare the LEFM predic-

Infobox 5. Experiments by Fineberg et al.

Infobox 2. Surface roughness and consequent argument that reconciles Da Vinci's experimental observations.

Surfaces are rough at the (sub)micrometre scale due to surface formation by fracture, microstructural influences, and/or machining. The local 'hills', or asperities, have a typical width of $1\mu\text{m}$ and are spaced $100\mu\text{m}$; a typical ratio of the real and the nominal area of contact is $A/A_0 = 10^{-3}$ (though different systems can display values that differ by (an) order(s) of magnitude). See diagram, from [14].

At the macroscopic scale, friction is defined according to the proportionality observed by Da Vinci through the friction coefficient $\mu = F/W$. The independence of the contact area follows by arguing that asperities detach when they reach a yield (shear) stress σ_y . Hence, $F = \sigma_y A$. The weight is, furthermore, argued to be sufficiently high for the asperity to behave plastically, responding at a constant stress $W = HA$ (with H the hardness of the material). The friction coefficient is then $\mu = \sigma_y/H$, independent of A and A_0 .

Infobox 3. Phenomenological rate-and-state model (macroscopic).

A rate-and-state model phenomenologically describes the evolution of the friction coefficient as follows

$$\mu = \mu_0 + A \ln \left(\frac{V}{V^*} + 1 \right) + B \ln \left(\frac{\theta}{\theta^*} + 1 \right), \quad \frac{d\theta}{dt} = 1 - \frac{\theta V}{D_c}$$

where V is the sliding velocity and θ is a state variable; μ_0 , A , B , V^* , and θ^* are constants. This gives rise to a transient length D_c and a steady state $\theta_{ss} = D_c/V$. D_c is the length over which the system loses memory, argued to be of the order of the asperity spacing.

Depicted is the predicted response to a velocity jump (top), and an example of an experimentally measured response for sliding of granite (bottom). The full diagram, from [9], in fact displays a similar behaviour for systems involving glass, plastic, steel, teflon, and wood.

Infobox 4. Burridge-Knopoff model predicting avalanches.

The Burridge-Knopoff model [29] is used to study friction by abstracting the bulk material as a set of point masses connected by springs whose sliding is mimicked using some phenomenological friction law. Beyond numerous numerical studies featuring different microscopic rules [30, 31, 31], such a model can be mapped on depinning models, for which (analytical) mean-field solutions are available [32–36]. Most notably, such depinning models predict that avalanche-sizes are scale-free. I.e. their distribution follows a power-law, known as Gutenberg-Richter's law, whereby the exponents can be predicted from mean-field solutions.

Diagram from [37].

tions to the measured strain field, which they are able to match with a remarkable degree of accuracy. Note once more that, compared to LEFM, one needs assume that the ‘fracture’ proceeds under a background stress: the stress that the interface can still carry after the rupture front passed.

Front velocity

The measurements of the rupture’s front velocity itself presents a puzzling picture. A wide range of front velocities are observed ranging from (i) “super-shear” (faster than the speed-of-sound in the solid, or more precisely the shear wave speed – one of the types of sound waves that can travel through a solid), via (ii) “Rayleigh” (around the speed-of-sound), to (iii) “sub-shear” (slower than the speed-of-sound). In particular the “super-shear” rupture fronts have fascinated scientists. It was found that such dynamics can be predicted using fracture mechanics, if one defines a certain interface law in which the fracture toughness decreases with increasing front velocity. What presents itself is known as the Andrew-Burridge mechanism [58–60], in which a rupture front accelerates towards the Rayleigh wave speed (about the speed-of-sound). The rupture front can then undergo a transition to become “super-shear”. This transition is accompanied by a ‘sonic boom’, as beautifully shown experimentally by Xia et al. [57] (see Fig. 2).

Figure 2. Transition to “super-shear” [57].

Currently, it is known that to observe “super-shear” rupture fronts, there has to be a microstructural velocity weakening fracture toughness and a sufficient amount of available elastic energy, but also that the heterogeneities of the interface matter [61, 62]. To understand the origin of velocity weakening toughness, precise microstructural arguments are lacking, though one could argue that travelling elastic waves that are generated by individual asperity detachments effectively weaken the other contacts, as they are accompanied by a peak stress that exceeds the stress redistribution that one expects from static arguments. To understand the entire range of front velocities one hypothesis, to be validated or falsified in the proposed project, is that the velocity simply depends on with the amount of built-up elastic energy at the moment of triggering the rupture front, whereby the mechanism of a velocity weakening fracture toughness always exists, but plays no special role for fronts that propagate at a velocity lower than the Rayleigh wave speed.

Nucleation

The perspective of treating friction as a fracture-like rupture process raises many questions. What, except for external triggering, plays the role of the seed-fracture? I.e. how do the detachments of individual asperities organise into a macroscopic crack? One can make several hypotheses about this. (1) A series of apparently uncorrelated detachments leads to an unstable region in which rupture percolates between the ‘damaged’ sites and then triggers the fracture. (2) The detachment of a single asperity triggers that of others, which triggers that of others. When, by chance, such an avalanche has a sufficiently large spatial extension, the fracture is triggered. (3) Each individual contact could be sufficiently strong, so that the elastic energy stored in the bulk could become sufficiently high, such that the detachment of one contact directly triggers fracture. Within the experimental accuracy of Fineberg and co-workers it is not clear that one can discriminate these scenarios. Even more so because slight inhomogeneities in the boundary conditions could favour one of the scenarios.

A clue could come from the earthquake community [63], where a power-law distribution of earthquake magnitudes is consistently found, which carries the name of the Gutenberg-Richter law [36, 64]. This seems to support the idea that the nucleation could be governed by avalanches. This, however, seems to be at odds with the idea of a fracture that propagates ballistically through the system.

The proposed project will seek a system validation or falsification of these hypotheses for different classes of systems.

3 Current state of personal research

An analogy with amorphous solids

To study the influence of disorder on friction, so far, mostly discrete models comparable to that due to Burridge and Knopoff [29] have been considered. A major disadvantage of such models is that elasticity is incorporated somewhat simplistically – in fact it is mostly short ranged (e.g. nearest-neighbour interaction). Inertia is subjected to the same limitations, while it is not considered in the mean field models. To truly incorporate long range elasticity the PI has drawn a parallel between the frictional problem and plasticity in an amorphous solid.

Amorphous solids, or glasses, as the name suggest, do not present any long-range order [65–67]. Whereas plasticity in a crystal proceeds by defects that move through the lattice. In a glass, plasticity proceeds by local particle rearrangements: a shear transformation. These rearrangements are coupled through elasticity. The release of elastic energy that accompanies the rearrangement can, through elastic coupling, trigger another rearrangement, which can trigger yet another rearrangement, etc. – an avalanche is formed [68–74]. In treating such a system as a continuum, one can imagine that a material point behaves elastically up to a certain threshold, or yield stress, beyond which the accumulated elastic energy is released. To model this, one can treat this mechanism using an energetic picture, wherein the material point is characterised by a quadratic potential around a certain minimum. Once it is excited beyond the threshold stress/strain, it jumps to a new minimum thereby releasing the elastic energy that was built up [75–80].

This picture strongly resembles what happens microscopically in the frictional interface: the asperities that are in contact are glued together. They thus respond elastically until they rupture once a certain yield stress is reached. One can thus abstract the frictional interface as a weak ‘amorphous’ layer embedded in an otherwise elastic solid. The key feature of this abstraction is that it does allow to capture the disordered nature of the interface while it otherwise treats the local complexities in an average sense.

This continuum model (see Infobox 6) provided access to well-established machinery from continuum mechanics, in which inertia and long range elasticity are well treated. Also numerical solutions using, in the PI’s case, the Finite Element Method, are well established. This has allowed the construction and efficient implementation, that is robust enough to systematically treat ensembles of disordered realisations. Along the way, the PI has discovered the importance of having a cusp intersection of the quadratic potentials when studying the effect of inertia, as smoothing it effectively introduces damping [78].

Shear band formation and fracture

Beyond the modelling analogies between friction and plasticity in amorphous solids, the process of shear band formation poses an interesting analogy. In the community of amorphous solids, recently a major interest has been drawn to so-called ultra-stable glasses. The stability refers here to the initial configuration of the glass, in the sense that there are only few sites where a particle rearrangement can be triggered. Such a configuration is obtained by a slow temperature quench starting from above the glass transition temperature. The reason of the recent interest is that such a process was so far impossible to mimic in simulations, but recently became tractable by a numerical trick known as a swap algorithm. The characteristic of the mechanical behaviour of such a glass is that an elastic regime is followed by a sudden macroscopic stress drop.

The PI, with co-workers [81], found that such a stress drop could be reproduced using a cellular automaton model (similar to Infobox 9, though entirely without inertia) by changing the distribution of yield stresses. We observed that the stress drop is formed by plastic strain that is highly localised in a shear band. We found that the picture of fracture fits the formation of the shear band well, in that sense that nucleation can be triggered by an imperfection of a size that depends on the difference between the stress at which the ‘failure’ is triggered, and the stress that a shear band can carry in a steady state. This opens up the opportunity to consider the frictional configuration as an (idealised) shear band in a stable glass, and in this way further study its nucleation.

Hysteresis

Returning to the continuum model, an interesting opportunity opens up, precisely because inertia is treated in a realistic way. In the community of depinning (avalanches), the role of inertia has been strongly debated. A particular uncertainty is whether inertia is responsible for hysteretic stick-slip behaviour [82, 83]. Furthermore it remains uncertain if the avalanche characteristics are different in the presence of inertia.

The PI found that crucial ingredients that help to clarify this problem are stability and fracture [77]. In particular, from fracture, a critical size (spatial extension) can be identified for which a weak region will propagate in an unstable way through the system. This size depends on the stress at which the system operates, compared to the stress that can be carried when the system slips. The weak region was found to be formed by avalanches, which were characterised in terms of the relationship between their size and spatial extension: their fractal dimension; and in terms of the exponent that characterises their power-law distribution. To provide a scaling relation for the number of avalanches that are triggered for a certain system size, the stability distribution (the distribution of the distance to failure of each point) was used. Putting this together provides a scaling relation for the stress drop caused by ‘fracture’ nucleated by an avalanches. It was found that as the system’s size increases, the stress drop becomes smaller. However, the scaling with the system size is so slow that any realistic system will display hysteresis, and thus stick-slip.

At the same time the PI studied the transition between two regimes: the inertial regime described above, and an overdamped regime in which the elastic waves are suppressed (which is studied by the field of depinning). It was found that while the inertial regime features fracture-like macroscopic stress drops, the overdamped regime is dominated by an avalanche-like response, with exponents matching those predicted by mean field theories [79], characterised by a smooth stress-strain response (that has vanishing stress drops already for finite systems), see Fig. 3.

Effective microscopic length scale

So far, the elasticity of the weak layer was assumed to be that of the bulk. One can easily imagine the slender asperities to be less rigid than the bulk. By reducing the elastic stiffness of the weak layer compared to that of the bulk the PI found that this phase contrast introduces a length scale on top of the intrinsic length scale of the disorder that was introduced in the model [84]. This length scale, over which the asperities effectively behave as a ‘super-asperity’, grows as the weak layer becomes less rigid. For a given system size this implies that, as the weak layer becomes less rigid, the system’s response transforms from fracture-like to avalanche-like.

Percolation effectively forming a seed crack

Before studying friction, in his PhD, the PI has studied the nucleation of fracture in an environment with a stronger disorder [85–91]. This involved a microstructure made up of two phases with strongly contrasting failure properties. Through smart ensemble averages, the PI has identified the local configuration most prone to void nucleation. The PI then identified the percolation mechanism that is responsible to effectively form a seed crack that grows unstably, resulting in macroscopic failure. In particular the type of observables that the PI developed during his PhD will be helpful in answering some of the research questions below.

Figure 3. (a,b) Typical stress-strain response, and (c) avalanche size distribution; for different degrees of dissipation ($\nu = 10$ approximates overdamped dynamics, $\nu = 0$ corresponds to the inertial case.)

Infobox 6. PI's novel model of friction: *continuum and disordered*.

The continuum model comprises a frictional interface embedded as a weak layer between two elastic bodies. This problem is governed by the following equation of motion:

$$\rho \ddot{\vec{u}} = \vec{\nabla} \cdot \vec{\sigma}(\vec{x}) - \alpha \dot{\vec{u}}(\vec{x})$$

featuring, from left to right, the inertial term, with ρ the mass density and $\ddot{\vec{u}}$ the acceleration; the divergence of the stress $\vec{\sigma}$; and a non-Rayleigh damping of the velocity $\dot{\vec{u}}$ introduced to avoid artefacts from the periodicity by damping waves whose wavelength is larger the system's size. A small strain assumption has been implicitly made. A weak layer is introduced (see below), that consists of a disordered set of blocks which mimic the behaviour of the asperity contacts. The rest of the geometry behaves linear elastically, i.e. according to a parabolic potential energy. The simplification is made that the response is (almost) incompressible by choosing the bulk modulus much higher than the shear modulus. The shear response is defined by a potential energy in terms of an equivalent deviatoric strain ε , that can be thought of as the amplitude of the deviatoric strain tensor. Plasticity is modelled by a series of parabolic potentials in strain space (with the same radius of curvature, to get a constant elastic modulus). Once the yield strain (or stress) is reached, the block 'jumps' to a new minimum. Note that the model is an extension of [75] in such a way that the model is now isotropic and applied to an inertial environment.

The yield strains are (currently) drawn from a Weibull distribution, which has been chosen to show no stress overshoot in the transition between the macroscopic elastic and plastic regimes. A crucial feature is that the magnitude of the typical yield strain ε_0 can be freely scaled, such as to scale down the deformation to respect the small strain assumption. Loading proceeds in a quasi-static protocol in which strain is applied in small steps. For efficiency, a step can be made arbitrarily large when all points respond elastically, resulting in an event-driven code.

The solution proceeds using the Finite Element Method (FEM) in combination with a time discretisation protocol. To this end, the domain is discretised in elements (as shown). Note that, by employing nodal quadrature to integrate the mass density, solving a system is avoided without strong physical assumptions.

4 Detailed research plan

It remains puzzling how to reconcile the pictures of avalanches and fracture, different rupture front velocities, and possible precursors to slip. The missing piece of knowledge that can establish their connection is how collective asperity detachments are organised, i.e. unravelling the nucleation of slip. Such a phenomenon happens on a mesoscale: there where the disorder matters, but its details may be treated in an effective way. *Three possible scenarios*, referred to as “mechanisms”, have been identified: percolation, avalanches, and fracture (see Infobox 7). Owing to the PI’s developed novel disordered but still continuum model of friction, unravelling nucleation in terms of important system features is possible for the first time (see Infoboxes 6 and 8). A *key asset* thereby is that physics at different length- and time-scales are introduced in a well-controlled manner, whereby access to all key observables is direct and transparent.

This project is aimed at identifying what combination of the system’s features (*the five ‘D’s of friction*) lead to what nucleation mechanism, and consequently, to what macroscopic observations in terms of stress-strain response, rupture front velocity, and event size distribution and spatial and temporal correlations. The emerging insights will then be brought together to determine which precursors to slip might be present. In short, the goals of this project are:

Infobox 7. Three scenarios – “mechanisms” – of slip nucleation.**Percolation**

The detachments happen at apparently *uncorrelated* locations. By this it is meant that they do not interact, but may display similar local features (see [85] for an example in a metal). When two damaged sites are sufficiently close, they will start interacting through the bulk’s elasticity. Consequently, a rupture will percolate and connect the two ‘damaged’ regions. Occasionally, when the damaged region is sufficiently large (whereby the critical size depends on the stress, in accordance with Griffith’s arguments), macroscopic slip will happen, a ‘fracture’ is thus observed. The expected signature is a stress-strain response without any clear pattern. The only ‘intrinsic’ stress is σ_c , the stress that a slipping interface can carry.

Avalanches

The detachment of a single asperity triggers other detachments in the neighbourhood, which triggers that of yet others in their neighbourhood. It is, however, distinctly different from a fracture, as there is not clear rupture front. Consequently, the avalanche’s spatial extension grows in some fractal way. In this scenario, the competition between the available elastic energy and the ‘force’ introduced by the disorder *likely causes the avalanche to stop*. This process of getting pinned to, and being depinned from, the disorder happens around a critical stress σ_c . The expected stress-strain signal is expected to display small fluctuation around σ_c . The avalanches are expected to be scale-free and universal, though different universality classes might govern different system configurations.

The signature of avalanches can be characterised from their statistics. The power-law exponent τ can be extracted from the distribution of avalanche sizes $\rho(S) \sim S^{-\tau}$ (transparently defined as the total number of yielding events during a load increment). The fractal dimension characterises the relationship between the avalanche size S and its spatial extension ξ , $S \sim \xi^{d_f}$, the latter being the maximum distance between blocks that yielded at least once during the load increment (note that this also leads to a measure of velocity as $\partial\xi/\partial t$).

The goal is to argue the universality of avalanches within a class of systems. Based on the PI’s recent work it is expected that the fact that an avalanche by chance can grow unstably does not change their universality [77]. Rather, their signature helps us to understand when they will grow unstably.

Fracture

A single weakest link triggers a well-defined rupture front that travels ballistically through the system. The expected stress-strain signal is expected to display finite stress drops, whereby the ‘top’ stress, at which the fracture nucleates, as well as the ‘bottom’ stress are expected to be well defined. The former being defined by the nature of the weakest link, while the latter is σ_c , the stress that the weak layer can carry in during slip. Note that also here $\partial\xi/\partial t$ provides a transparent measure for the front’s velocity.

4.1 Construct 5-d mechanism map

The goal is to create a five-dimensional mechanism map, identifying which nucleation mechanism dominates which combination of five key features that govern any frictional problem – *the five 'D's of friction*. These features are: Disorder, Dissipation (along the interface), Drive (imposed strain vs. imposed stress), Dimensionality (two- vs. three-dimensions), and Delay (age of the interface). To explore this space efficiently, the configuration used so far in the PI's work will serve as a reference, compared to which a variation is studied along each of the five axes. Based on these insights a decision will be made to probe relevant 'cross-terms' (featuring more than one variation). A key remark thereby is that it cannot be established a-priori that different combinations of variations cannot have the same effect, likely rendering only specific combinations of the variations relevant.

Disorder

The effect that the degree and type of disorder has on the nucleation mechanism, is one of the key contributions of this work as it has very little overlap with existing studies, which are usually either performed at the millimetre scale at which predictions are made using effective phenomenological models, or at the micro- or nanometre scale at which studying disorder at lengths scales longer than one micrometre is impossible. In both cases, the emergent effects that arise from the disorder are missed. Here, three cases will be studied:

1. *Two intrinsic length scales.* As described in Sec. 3, the PI has discovered that the elastic properties in the weak layer introduce a second length scale in the problem. As the elastic modulus of the weak layer is reduced, the asperities (the disordered blocks) start acting as a 'super-asperity'. This discovery will be exploited to systematically introduce disorder along two length scales: the yield strains of the blocks vary in space, while their elastic modulus also varies across a longer length scale, as illustrated in Fig. 4(a). The question is: which length scale dominates? This study is a step towards understanding the relevance of the fractal nature of the surface, whereby a surface is rough at any scale. If it can be argued why a specific scale will dominate nucleation, a study involving the full fractal nature of surfaces may not be needed.
2. *Spatial sparsity of contacts.* As described in Infobox 2, a frictional configuration might only have a minor number of contacts in space – the real area of contact is just a fraction of the apparent area of contact. In the PI's energetic picture this corresponds to introducing flat directions: directions in which a material point can move without any energy cost. This can be easily introduced in the disorder of the block, see Fig. 4(b). Making contacts scarcer will likely hinder the possibility of individual events to organise.
3. *Rare events.* As described in Sec. 3, a surprising discovery has been that rare events can switch the nucleation mechanisms from fracture to avalanches, whereby the argument was that also in a stable system (that results from a system spanning avalanche). Its low efficiency caused the inertial system to be dominated by fracture in finite sized systems, but by avalanches in the thermodynamic limit. A question is if the introduction of rare weak sites can trigger nucleation by avalanches in relative small systems. An equally interesting case to study is that of rare strong sites. Both are done by biasing the distributions from which the yield strains are drawn, see Fig. 4(c). This way, their efficiency in a finite sized system can be systematically checked.

Dissipation

There are several possible mechanisms that dissipate energy. They include bulk materials that dissipate energy, various dissipation mechanisms of the asperity contacts, or dissipation by third body interaction at the interface (like dust particles, fluids, gauge material). This dissipation is introduced in the model using a viscous term, resulting in the following equation of motion

$$\rho \ddot{\mathbf{u}} = \vec{\nabla} \cdot \left(\boldsymbol{\sigma}(\vec{x}) + \eta \vec{\nabla}_s \dot{\mathbf{u}} \right) + \alpha \dot{\mathbf{u}}$$

where η is the viscosity, that is considered as the ratio $\nu = \eta/\rho$. There are two clear extremes: $\nu = 0$ corresponds to no damping, while for $\nu > 1$ any wave whose wavelength is larger than that of the discretisation is damped.

So far, the PI has performed a study in which ν was continuously varied between 0 and 100, however, such that it was homogeneous in space (see Fig. 3). This effectively changed the bulk material to present a rubber-like behaviour. The result is summarised in Fig. 5 as a sketch of the mechanism map along the dissipation axis. As observed, the nucleation mechanism changes from avalanches to fracture (see also Fig. 3).

This project will not consider dissipation in the bulk, but only in the weak layer. ν will thus be non-zero in the weak layer. The first question is whether this kind of dissipation is as effective as introducing dissipation everywhere. The second case to study is the effect of introducing a dissipating, weak, third body, as shown in Fig. 4(d), mimicking gauge in earthquakes or a lubricant in friction. The picture thus changes from asperity detachment to shear band formation. The hypothesis is that the extra freedom of a moving front ‘bypassing’ strong sites will reduce the friction. In terms of nucleation it is difficult to say what happens. On the one hand, an avalanche or fracture can always be localised to one layer. On the other hand, percolation of damage in the different layers is perceivable in a strongly disordered environment.

Drive

In the studied system, the boundaries are uniformly driven using a prescribed strain protocol. Through the elasticity of the bulk, this results in some intermediate protocol at the level of the interface, between imposed strain and imposed stress. The controlling parameter is thereby the height H of the bulk. In terms of the drive, the weak layer experiences the loading frame (the top boundary) through a ‘spring’ whose stiffness scales as $1/H$. A systematic variation of H corresponds to a systematic variation of the driving protocol. The pitfall here lies in the elastic waves, because the top and boundary reflect those waves. A small H will thus also effectively heat the system, which could be physical but should be studied as a

separate effect. For this, a vectorial version of the non-Rayleigh damping is proposed as $\vec{\alpha} \cdot \dot{\vec{u}}$, whereby the components of $\vec{\alpha}$ will be chosen to critically damp any wave whose wave-length is longer than L and H respectively.

The question to answer here is whether the system displays stick-slip when driven in imposed strain, as is observed for macroscopic models. An hypothesis is that for the same disorder the nucleation is forced to change from avalanches to percolation or fracture.

The second question is if the nucleation mechanism can be changed by (slightly) non-uniform boundary conditions. This is probably always the case experimentally, and might thus connect the experiments of Fineberg et al. and the Gutenberg-Richter law observed in earthquakes.

Dimensionality

Besides the two-dimensional geometry that is used as a reference, the study is extended to three dimensions, such that rupture has to proceed, at least partly, in two dimensions. This is not a trivial step, as nucleation might proceed in a different way compared to the slender, two-dimensional, geometry; even for the same shear load imposed on the top boundary (while both other boundaries will be assumed periodic). It is foreseeable that an effective pre-crack is not so easy to find in the system. It is thus more likely that nucleation proceeds by avalanches or percolation. The important question to address here is how the different layers of asperities interact: whether they act as an effective asperity with average properties, or whether they are dominated by the weakest asperity.

Delay

Here it will be considered that aging of the interface effectively changes the yield stresses (which somewhat effectively also captures that the real contact area evolves because of time relaxation mechanisms [17, 92–94]). This can be easily incorporated in the model by letting the yield strain grow with the waiting time as $\varepsilon_{yi} = \varepsilon_{y0i}(1 + (t - t_{yi}))$, where ε_{y0i} is the reference yield strain that grows with the time since the block yield last, $t - t_{yi}$, see Fig. 6. A more direct evolution of contact area is also feasible when applied to the flat directions in the potential, as in Fig. 4(b). A hypothesis is that rare strong sites will start dominating. When they stay stuck for a long time, the stress can increase significantly and the nucleation mechanism can switch from avalanches to fracture. The increase in stress is expected to be reflected in faster-moving rupture fronts.

Figure 6. Aging of contacts

Even though this is a seemingly simple variation, there is one important feature to this protocol: the location of the current minimum cannot change. This implies that the yield strain has to grow in the same way in both directions. To do so systematically, using one integration point will be considered. This most likely cannot be accomplished with the current incompressible material, so this also requires the exploration of the effect of Poisson's ratio. Student projects will be used to explore these uncertainties.

4.2 Rationalise slip front dynamics

In Section 2, the hypothesis was postulated that the rupture front velocity of the ultimate fracture depends simply on the amount of build up elastic energy. If this is true, the rupture front velocity can likely be connected to the nucleation mechanism, as it will ultimately determine the stress at which the final fracture is nucleated. The rupture front velocity and its reproducibility can then teach us something about the nucleation mechanism in real systems.

To test these hypotheses, the first thing to check is if a rupture nucleated at different stresses indeed display a different front velocity. The second thing to check is if all experimentally observed front velocities can be reconciled by the inertial model, or if a dissipative mechanism is needed to reach the lower range of velocities. Both will be done by manually triggering fracture. With this insight, direct measurements in which the fracture results from some nucleation mechanism can be analysed.

5 Schedule and milestones

A series of student projects are used by the PI to perform exploration studies to execute actual study more efficiently. Part of these projects will benefit from a cellular automaton model as was used by the PI in [81] (see Infobox 9). None of these theses are essential to reach the proposed project goals. Note, furthermore, that the study of the rupture front velocity and possible precursors is considered an integral part of those systems where the relevant nucleation mechanism is present. Depending on early outcomes, it will be decided if the study of these observables is always relevant.

Project	PI				Implementation				Student project							
	1.1	1.2	1.3	1.4	2.1	2.2	2.3	2.4	3.1	3.2	3.3	3.4	4.1	4.2	4.3	4.4
Disorder 1 (two length scales)																
Disorder 2 (flat directions)																
Disorder 3 (rare events)																
Drive																
Dissipation (third body)																
Dimensionality (3-d)																
Parallel implementation																
Cellular automaton																
Delay																
Explore compressible material																
Explore with cellular automaton																
Reduced quadrature (2-d & 3-d)																
Triangular elements																
Full phase diagram																
Disorder vs. drive																
Disorder vs. dissipation																

Infobox 8. Practical implementation.

The PI’s code is based on the PI’s extensive expertise in FEM (and other techniques [95–98]) and the C++ programming language. It comprises a modular framework that gets its user-friendliness from multidimensional arrays. Such routines are currently provided by the PI’s own library cppmat [99]. Its feature set has been picked up by a professional developer team, that will port it into their library xtensor [100] (which features numerous optimisations), which is completed at the start of the Ambizione project.

In the FEM code, the only thing that remains to be done is efficient parallelisation to allow the three-dimensional study (that is otherwise restrictively slow). The fact that the simulations are embarrassingly parallel – an ensemble consists of many independent realisations – and the architecture of the computing facilities available at EPFL, make that the parallel architecture can employ a shared memory. Its implementation using OpenMP involves only minor additions to the existing code, that do not impede the readability, maintainability, and existing functionality. Given the PI’s extensive programming experience this is scheduled to take no more than three months.

Infobox 9. Cellular automaton (to be developed by students).

In addition to the precise continuum model a simple cellular automaton model will be developed, through student projects, for rapid exploration studies. Such model comprises a regular grid of blocks, each characterised by its shear and yield stress (drawn from some distribution). When a block fails, by incrementing the average stress, the block’s stress is redistributed using an elastic propagator [74, 101–103]. These overdamped dynamics can be complemented using a phenomenological inertial perturbation [83]. Compared to the continuum model, cellular automaton is only approximate, but much more efficient.

6 Relevance and impact

General impact

The main contribution of this Ambizione project, the mechanism map indicating how slip is nucleated as a function of the relevant parameters that govern friction, is expected to have high scientific and practical impact (see expected output below). It provides practical guidelines on how to rationalise a specific combination of observations acquired in laboratory friction or earthquake experiments [57] or in real earthquake measurements [104]; and it provides clear knobs that can be turned to systematically do scientific experiments and design. The potential direct societal impact is therefore two-fold:

Earthquake predictability

Understanding how an earthquake is nucleated can help us to further think about *predicting large earthquakes* based on the conditions that can lead up to the type of nucleation that results in such an event. So far, earthquake predictability is pursued through temporal correlations, but there is a strong scientific debate on how to choose the data that should be included in these correlations [105–108]. Having a clear idea how (major) earthquakes nucleate can rationalise this debate.

To get *firsthand capabilities* in this subject, a *discussion platform between the PI and the Swiss Seismological Service (SED) at ETH Zürich* is proposed as part of this Ambizione project. The SED's extensive expertise on the topic of earthquakes, their predictability, and capturing main features in a laboratory environment that provides rich and precise measurements will help the PI to bridge reality and his well-controlled environment [107, 109–114]. Both parties have committed themselves to have rounds of *informal discussions twice a year*, in which we will test, amongst others, the predictive capabilities of different realistic strategies for the different scenarios of nucleation.

Friction by design

Of course reducing frictional losses is one of the ultimate goals. This project is likely to yield an insight of the efficiency of a combination of strategies. However, further research should provide a wider context as some strategies, such as a 'simple' lubrication, partly present different physics that are not pursued here. Nonetheless, knowing how slip is nucleated, and what macroscopic consequence each mechanism has, provides clear practical guidelines to perform '*friction by design*'. Although not directly pursued in this project, one can imagine the need to tweak certain features of friction in designing high-precision equipment in which positioning over- or undershoots are unwanted. The proposed mechanism map, with links to macroscopic properties, can potentially uncover the need to make unintuitive choices whereby one may for example have to increase friction to change the nucleation mechanism to avoid such an unwanted behaviour.

Expected scientific output

- Unravelling the nucleation along each axis of the mechanism map will likely lead to at least one journal publication (thus *five journal publications in total*), in addition to *four to ten bachelor or master theses*. *One grand publication* will collect the entire picture. Publications of sub mechanism maps might be worth pursuing, as will be decided according to relevance.
- A proper understanding and prediction of the rupture front velocity is a hot topic that will likely lead to *at least one journal publication*.
- Exploration of earthquake predictability in the PI's numerical results will likely lead to *at least one journal publication*, hopefully in collaboration with the SED.
- Abstracts will be submitted to *two conferences or workshops per year per community* (mechanics and physics).
- The PI is committed to publishing his codes *open-source* (as he has done so far [76, 99, 115–117]). Crucial simulation data will be shared freely as much as possible within reasonable costs.

In addition to the SNFS' commitment to ensure Open Access of publications, the PI will submit preprints to arXiv.

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